

An existence principle for variational inequalities in Banach spaces

D. Ariza-Ruiz^a, J. Garcia-Falset^b, J. Villada-Bedoya^c

^a*Departamento de Análisis Matemático, Universidad de Sevilla, Apdo. 1160, 41080-Sevilla, Spain*

^b*Departament d'Anàlisi Matemàtica, Universitat de València, Dr. Moliner 50, 46100, Burjassot, València, Spain*

^c*Departamento de Matemáticas Básicas, Centro de investigación en Matemáticas (CIMAT), Col. Valenciana, Jalisco s/n, 36240 Guanajuato, Gto., México*

Abstract

The present article deals with existence and uniqueness results for a variational inequality posed on a real smooth Banach space. Which allows us to generalize the known results of this type given in Hilbert spaces.

Keywords: Variational inequalities, accretive operators, fixed points, zeroes of an operator.

MSC: 49J40, 47H06, 47H10.

1. Introduction

Let K be a nonempty closed convex subset of a real Hilbert space $(\mathbb{H}, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$. Let $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{H}$ be a mapping. The classical variational inequality problem is formulated as:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Find a point } x^* \in K \text{ such that} \\ \langle f(x^*), x - x^* \rangle \geq 0, \quad \forall x \in K \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Variational inequalities were initially studied by Kinderlehrer and Stampacchia [18] and ever since have been widely studied. This problem provides a broad unifying setting for the study of optimization, equilibrium and related problems and serves as a useful computational framework for the solution of a host of problems in very diverse applications. Variational inequalities have been a classical subject in mathematical physics, particularly in the calculus of variations associated with the minimization of infinite-dimensional functionals.

On the other hand, the systematic study of Projected Dynamical Systems (PDS) on infinite dimensional Hilbert spaces was initiated by several authors among them,

Email addresses: dariza@us.es (D. Ariza-Ruiz), garciaf@uv.es (the corresponding author) (J. Garcia-Falset), jeimer.villada@cimat.mx (J. Villada-Bedoya)

Cojocaru, Daniele, Isac, Nagurney [6, 7, 15], this new concept was applied to the study of Evolutionary variational inequalities (EVI) by showing that the critical points (i.e., equilibrium points) of (PDS) are exactly the solutions of the (EVI). The (PDS) is a differential equation involving the metric projection. Later on, Giuffrè *at el.* [13] studied this problem in a general reflexive, strictly convex and smooth Banach space by using a new concept of projection.

In this paper, motivated by the above comments, we consider the following generalized variational inequality problem in Banach spaces (see [2]): Let K be a nonempty closed convex subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} and let $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ be a mapping. Find a point $u \in K$ such that

$$VI(f, K) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Find } u \in K \text{ such that} \\ \langle f(u), J(v - u) \rangle \geq 0, \quad \forall v \in K, \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

where J is the normalized duality mapping of \mathbb{B} into \mathbb{B}^* .

This problem is connected with the fixed point problem for nonlinear mappings as well as the question of finding a zero of a nonlinear mapping.

Finally, in the last section we focus on the relationship between a projected dynamical system and the above variational inequality.

2. Notations and Preliminaries

Let $(\mathbb{B}, \|\cdot\|)$ be a real Banach space and \mathbb{B}^* its topological dual. As usual, $B_r(x)$ and $S_r(x)$ denote the closed ball and the sphere of center x and radius r respectively. If $x \in \mathbb{B}$ we shall denote by $J(x)$ the normalized duality mapping at x defined by $J(x) := \{j \in \mathbb{B}^* : \langle x, j \rangle := j(x) = \|x\|^2, \|j\| = \|x\|\}$. In general, the normalized duality mapping $J : \mathbb{B} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{B}^*}$ is multi-valued. We list some properties below for easy reference (see [5, 19] for more details).

- (P₁) For any $x \in \mathbb{B}$, $J(x)$ is nonempty, bounded, closed and convex.
- (P₂) For any $x \in \mathbb{B}$ and a real number α , $J(\alpha x) = \alpha J(x)$.
- (P₃) For any $x, y \in \mathbb{B}$, $\varphi \in J(x)$ and $\psi \in J(y)$, $\langle x - y, \varphi - \psi \rangle \geq 0$.
- (P₄) For any $x, y \in \mathbb{B}$ and $\psi \in J(y)$, $\langle x - y, \psi \rangle \leq \|x\|^2 - \|y\|^2$.
- (P₅) If \mathbb{B} is strictly convex, J is one-to-one.
- (P₆) If \mathbb{B} is reflexive, J is a mapping of X onto X^* .
- (P₇) If \mathbb{B} is smooth, J is a single-valued mapping.

(P₈) If \mathbb{B} is smooth, strictly convex and reflexive, then J is single-valued, one-to-one and onto. In this case, the duality mapping J^* from \mathbb{B}^* to \mathbb{B} is the inverse of J , that is, $J^* = J^{-1}$.

(P₉) J is continuous in smooth Banach spaces.

A mapping $A : \mathbb{B} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{B}}$ will be called an operator on a Banach space \mathbb{B} . The domain of A is denoted by $\mathcal{D}(A)$ and its range by $\mathcal{R}(A)$. An operator A on \mathbb{B} is said to be *accretive* if the inequality $\|x - y + \lambda(u - v)\| \geq \|x - y\|$ holds for all $\lambda \geq 0$, $x, y \in \mathcal{D}(A)$ and $u \in A(x)$, $v \in A(y)$. If, in addition, $\mathcal{R}(I + \lambda A)$ (i.e., the range of the operator $I + \lambda A$), is for one, hence for all, $\lambda > 0$, precisely \mathbb{B} , then A is called *m-accretive*. Nevertheless, if $\overline{\mathcal{D}(A)} \subseteq \bigcap_{\lambda > 0} \mathcal{R}(I + \lambda A)$, then A is said to have the range condition. Accretive operators were introduced by Browder [4] and Kato [17] independently.

The resolvent of an operator $A : \mathcal{D}(A) \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{B}}$ is defined as $\mathcal{J}_\lambda := (I + \lambda A)^{-1}$, and the Yosida approximant of A as $\mathcal{A}_\lambda := \frac{1}{\lambda}(I - \mathcal{J}_\lambda)$.

We now recall some important facts regarding accretive operators which will be used in our paper (see, for instance, [5, 19]).

Proposition 2.1. *Let \mathbb{B} be a Banach space.*

- (a) *An operator $A : \mathbb{B} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{B}}$ is accretive if and only if for each $x, y \in \mathcal{D}(A)$ and for each $u \in A(x)$ and $v \in A(y)$ there exists $j(x - y) \in J(x - y)$ such that $\langle u - v, j(x - y) \rangle \geq 0$.*
- (b) *An operator $A : \mathbb{B} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{B}}$ is accretive if and only if for each $\lambda > 0$, the resolvent \mathcal{J}_λ is a single-valued nonexpansive mapping, that is, $\|\mathcal{J}_\lambda(x) - \mathcal{J}_\lambda(y)\| \leq \|x - y\|$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{R}(I + \lambda A)$.*
- (c) *For all $x \in \mathcal{R}(I + \lambda A)$ and for each $\lambda > 0$, $\mathcal{A}_\lambda x \in A\mathcal{J}_\lambda x$.*

When A is an accretive operator which satisfies the range condition we have

- (d) *For all $x \in \mathcal{D}(A)$ and $\lambda > 0$, $\|\mathcal{A}_\lambda x\| \leq |Ax| := \inf\{\|y\| : y \in Ax\}$.*
- (e) *Given $x \in \mathcal{D}(A)$, the mapping $\lambda \mapsto \mathcal{J}_\lambda x$ is continuous for $\lambda \geq 0$, with $\mathcal{J}_0 x = x$.*

For the sake of simplicity and clarity, throughout this paper we assume that \mathbb{B} is a real *smooth* Banach space; hence, the normalized duality mapping $J : \mathbb{B} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{B}^*}$ is single-valued.

We denote by Ψ the set of continuous functionals $\psi : \mathbb{B} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ such that $\psi(0) = 0$, $\psi(x) > 0$ for $x \in \mathbb{B} \setminus \{0\}$ and which satisfy the following condition:

For every sequence $\{x_n\}$ in \mathbb{B} such that $\{\|x_n\|\}$ is decreasing and $\psi(x_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $\|x_n\| \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Definition 2.1. Let K be a nonempty subset of \mathbb{B} . A mapping $f : K \rightarrow X$ is said to be

- (i) strictly accretive if $\langle f(x) - f(y), j(x - y) \rangle > 0$ for all $x, y \in K$ with $x \neq y$.
- (ii) strongly accretive if there exists a positive real number η such that $\eta\|x - y\|^2 \leq \langle f(x) - f(y), J(x - y) \rangle$ for all $x, y \in K$.
- (ii) ϕ -strongly accretive if there exists a continuous function $\phi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ with $\phi^{-1}(0) = \{0\}$ such that $\phi(\|x - y\|)\|x - y\| \leq \langle f(x) - f(y), J(x - y) \rangle$ for all $x, y \in K$.
- (iii) ϕ -accretive at zero if there exist $\psi \in \Psi$ and a point $z_0 \in K$ such that $\psi(x - z_0) \leq \langle f(x), J(x - z_0) \rangle$ for all $x \in K$.
- (iv) coercitive at $x_0 \in K$ if $\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle f(x) - f(x_0), J(x - x_0) \rangle}{\|x - x_0\|} = +\infty$.

Given K a nonempty, closed and convex subset of a real smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} and $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ a nonlinear mapping. The variational inequality defined by K and f denoted by $\mathbf{VI}(K, f)$ is the problem of finding an element $u \in K$ such that

$$\langle f(u), J(x - u) \rangle \geq 0, \quad \text{for all } x \in K. \quad (3)$$

Definition 2.2. Let K be a closed convex subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . We define the normal cone of K in x to be the set

$$N_K(x) := \{ \xi \in \mathbb{B} : \langle \xi, J(z - x) \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall z \in K \}$$

Remark 2.1. Note that if x belongs to the interior of K , then $N_K(x) = \{0\}$. Indeed, suppose that $\xi \in N_K(x)$. Since $x \in \text{int}(K)$ there exists $\rho > 0$ such that $x + \rho\xi \in K$. Thus, since $\xi \in N_K(x)$, $\langle \xi, J(x + \rho\xi - x) \rangle \leq 0 \iff \rho \langle \xi, J(\xi) \rangle \leq 0 \iff \xi = 0$.

Lemma 2.1. Let K be a closed convex subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . The multivalued mapping $N_K : K \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{B}}$ is accretive with the range condition.

Proof. Note that N_K has the range condition because given $y \in K$, $0 \in \lambda N_K(y)$ for any $\lambda > 0$, and therefore taking $x = y$ we get $y \in x + \lambda N_K(x)$, for any $\lambda > 0$.

Let us prove that N_K is accretive. For every $y_i \in N_K(x_i)$, with $i = 1, 2$, from the properties of the duality mapping we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle y_1 - y_2, J(x_1 - x_2) \rangle &= \langle y_1, J(x_1 - x_2) \rangle - \langle y_2, J(x_1 - x_2) \rangle \\ &= -\langle y_1, J(x_2 - x_1) \rangle - \langle y_2, J(x_1 - x_2) \rangle \geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

since $y_i \in N_K(x_i)$. □

Remark 2.2. Notice that the variational inequality (3) has a solution either if there exists $u \in K$ such that $f(u) = 0$ or if there exists $u \in K$ such that $0 \in \mathcal{R}(N_k + f)$.

Now we recall several concepts and facts related to Fixed Point Theory, which will be used throughout the paper.

Let C be a nonempty set of a Banach space \mathbb{B} and let $T : C \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ be a mapping. We say that T is nonexpansive if $\|T(x) - T(y)\| \leq \|x - y\|$ for all $x, y \in C$. A sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in C is said to be an approximate fixed point sequence for T whenever $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|T(x_n) - x_n\| = 0$. The following result is a particular case of Theorem 3.9 in [11] for nonexpansive mappings.

Theorem 2.1. *Let C be a closed convex and unbounded subset of a Banach space \mathbb{B} and let $T : C \rightarrow C$ be a nonexpansive mapping. The following statements are equivalent:*

- (a) *There exists a bounded almost fixed point sequence for T in C ,*
- (b) *There exist $x_0 \in C$ and $R > 0$ such that $T(x) - x_0 \neq \lambda(x - x_0)$ for all $\lambda > 1$ and for all $x \in C \cap S_R(x_0)$.*

3. Existence of solution for the variational inequality

3.1. General considerations

Let us consider the following condition which will be useful in this paper.

Definition 3.1. Let K be a subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . A mapping $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is said to satisfy condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$ if there exist $R > 0$ and $z \in K$ such that $\langle f(x), J(x - z) \rangle \geq 0$ for all $x \in K \cap S_R(z)$.

We next show that condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$ becomes necessary for existence of a solution of the variational inequality $VI(f, K)$ whenever f is an accretive mapping.

Proposition 3.1. *Let K be a closed convex subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . Let $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ be accretive. If the problem $VI(f, K)$ has a solution, then f satisfies condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$.*

Proof. By contradiction, suppose that condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$ fails. In this case, given an arbitrary $x \in K$ there exist a sequence of elements of K (y_n), such that $\|y_n\| \rightarrow \infty$ (this means K is unbounded) and $\langle f(y_n), J(y_n - x) \rangle < 0$. Since f is an accretive mapping, it satisfies $\langle f(x) - f(y_n), J(x - y_n) \rangle \geq 0$. Therefore,

$$\langle f(x), J(y_n - x) \rangle \leq \langle f(y_n), J(y_n - x) \rangle < 0$$

The last inequality means that $VI(f, K)$ cannot have any solution. □

Although condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$ seems artificial, there are many accretive mappings satisfying this condition, for example the ψ -accretive mappings or the coercitive mappings, even a more general class of mappings which include to coercitive mappings.

Proposition 3.2. *Let K be a subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . If $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is ψ -accretive at zero then f enjoys condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$.*

Proof. Since f is accretive at zero, there exist $\psi \in \Phi$ and $z_0 \in K$ such that $\langle f(x), J(x - z_0) \rangle \geq \psi(x - z_0)$ for all $x \in K$. Since $\psi(y) > 0$ for all $y \neq 0$, we have $\langle f(x), J(x - z_0) \rangle > 0$ for all $x \in K$ with $x \neq z_0$. In particular, f satisfies condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$ with $z = z_0$ and for any $R > 0$. \square

We now show that condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$ holds for the coercitive mappings, even for a more general class of mappings which include to coercitive mappings.

Definition 3.2. Let K be a subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . A mapping $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ said to satisfy the general coercitivity condition at $x_0 \in K$ if

$$\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle f(x) - f(x_0), J(x - x_0) \rangle}{\|x - x_0\|} > \|f(x_0)\|.$$

Remark 3.1. The class of mappings satisfying the general coercitivity condition is strictly larger than the class of coercitive mappings. For instance, any function $f : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, such that $f(x) \rightarrow L > |f(0)| + f(0)$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$, satisfies the general coercitivity condition at $x_0 = 0$ but f is not coercitive at any point.

Proposition 3.3. *Let K be a subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . If $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ satisfies the general coercivity condition at $x_0 \in K$ then condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$ holds for $z = x_0$.*

Proof. Let us see that there exists $R > 0$ such that $\langle f(x), j(x - x_0) \rangle \geq 0$ for every $x \in K \cap S_R(x_0)$. Consider $h > 0$ such that $\|f(x_0)\| < h \leq \ell$, where

$$\ell = \lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle f(x) - f(x_0), J(x - x_0) \rangle}{\|x - x_0\|}.$$

Since f satisfies the general coercivity at x_0 , there exists $R > 0$ such that

$$\langle f(x) - f(x_0), J(x - x_0) \rangle \geq h \|x - x_0\| \quad \forall x \in K \cap S_R(x_0),$$

consequently

$$\langle f(x), J(x - x_0) \rangle \geq h \|x - x_0\| - \langle f(x_0), J(x - x_0) \rangle \quad \forall x \in K \cap S_R(x_0),$$

which implies

$$\begin{aligned} \langle f(x), J(x - x_0) \rangle &\geq h \|x - x_0\| - \|f(x_0)\| \|x - x_0\| \\ &= (h - \|f(x_0)\|) \|x - x_0\| \geq 0 \quad \forall x \in K \cap S_R(x_0). \end{aligned}$$

\square

Proposition 3.4. *Let K be a subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . Assume that $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is a ϕ -strongly accretive mapping. If there exists $x_0 \in K$ such that $\lim_{r \rightarrow +\infty} \phi(r) > \|f(x_0)\|$, then f is generalized coercitive at x_0 and, therefore, f satisfies condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$ for $z = x_0$.*

Proof. Since f is ϕ -strongly accretive, for any $x \in K$ we have

$$\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle f(x) - f(x_0), J(x - x_0) \rangle}{\|x - x_0\|} \geq \lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} \phi(\|x - x_0\|) = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} \phi(r) > \|f(x_0)\|,$$

which means that f is generalized coercitive at x_0 . \square

Remark 3.2. If $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is ϕ -strongly accretive with $\phi(r) \rightarrow \infty$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$ or if f is strongly accretive, then the hypothesis of the above result holds.

In [10] the author proves that every m - ϕ -strong accretive operator is in fact an m - ψ -accretive operator at zero. In our context, the implication every ϕ -strong accretive operator is ψ -accretive operator at zero remains true whenever the variational inequality $V(f, K)$ has a solution. Namely,

Proposition 3.5. *Let K be a subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . Assume that $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is a ϕ -strongly accretive mapping. If the variational inequality $VI(f, K)$ has a solution, then f is ψ -accretive at zero.*

Proof. By hypothesis, there exists $u \in K$ such that $\langle f(u), J(x - u) \rangle \geq 0$ for all $x \in K$. Since f is ϕ -strongly accretive we get

$$\langle f(x), J(x - u) \rangle \geq \phi(\|x - u\|) \|x - u\| + \langle f(u), J(x - u) \rangle \geq \phi(\|x - u\|) \|x - u\|.$$

Thus, if we define $\psi(x) := \phi(\|x\|) \|x\|$ we obtain that f is ψ -accretive at zero with $z_0 = u$. \square

In general, for strictly accretive mappings we can ensure the uniqueness of the variational problem whenever the existence holds.

Proposition 3.6. *Let K be a subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . Let $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ be strictly accretive. If the problem $VI(f, K)$ has a solution, then it is unique.*

Proof. Let x_1, x_2 be two solutions to the problem $VI(f, K)$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Then, for $i = 1, 2$, $\langle f(x_i), J(x - x_i) \rangle \geq 0$ for all $x \in K$. In particular for $x = x_2$ and $x = x_1$, we have $\langle f(x_1), J(x_2 - x_1) \rangle \geq 0$ and $\langle f(x_2), J(x_1 - x_2) \rangle \geq 0$, respectively. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq \langle f(x_1), J(x_2 - x_1) \rangle + \langle f(x_2), J(x_1 - x_2) \rangle \\ &= \langle f(x_1), J(x_2 - x_1) \rangle - \langle f(x_2), J(x_2 - x_1) \rangle \\ &= \langle f(x_1) - f(x_2), J(x_2 - x_1) \rangle, \end{aligned}$$

that is, $\langle f(x_1) - f(x_2), J(x_1 - x_2) \rangle \leq 0$, which is a contradiction with the strict accretivity of f . \square

Note that the ψ -accretiveness at zero does not implies the strict accretiveness. For example, given $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $b \geq 0$, the function $f : [a, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, defined by $f(x) = b$, is ψ -accretive at zero for $\psi(t) = t$ and $z_0 = a$ but f is not strictly accretive. Hence, the above result cannot be applied to ψ -accretive at zero mappings. But for this class of mappings we also have uniqueness of solutions of the variational inequality $VI(f, K)$.

Proposition 3.7. *Let K be a subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . Let $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ be ψ -accretive at zero. If the problem $VI(f, K)$ has a solution, then it is unique.*

Proof. By hypothesis, we know that there exist $\psi \in \Phi$ and $z_0 \in K$ such that $\langle f(x), J(x - z_0) \rangle \geq \psi(x - z_0)$ for all $x \in K$.

Suppose that x_1, x_2 are two solutions to the variational inequality $VI(f, K)$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Then, for $i = 1, 2$, $\langle f(x_i), J(x - x_i) \rangle \geq 0$ for all $x \in K$. In particular for $x = z_0$ we have $0 \geq \langle f(x_i), J(x_i - z_0) \rangle \geq \psi(x_i - z_0) \geq 0$. Hence, $\psi(x_i - z_0) = 0$. Since $\psi \in \Phi$, we have $x_i = z_0$, which proves that the unique solution of $VI(f, K)$ is the point z_0 . \square

Next we will focus on providing conditions that guarantee the existence of solutions of variational inequality $VI(f, K)$. In order to do this, we distinguish two cases: when the space has the Fixed Point Property or not.

3.2. Assuming that X has the FPP

Recall that a Banach space \mathbb{B} satisfies the *Fixed Point Property* (the FPP, in short) whenever each nonexpansive self-mapping of each nonempty closed convex bounded subset of \mathbb{B} has a fixed point, see [14].

Theorem 3.1. *Let \mathbb{B} be a smooth space with the FPP and $K \subset \mathbb{B}$ a closed convex set. If $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is an accretive mapping and $f + N_K$ has the range condition, then the following conditions are equivalent.*

- (a) *the variational inequality $VI(f, K)$ has a solution,*
- (b) *f satisfies condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$.*

Proof. We just prove (b) \Rightarrow (a), because the converse implication is obtained from Proposition 3.1. Let $A = N_K + f$. Since f and N_K are accretive, A is also accretive and since by hypothesis A has the range condition, then $\mathcal{J}_1^A : K \rightarrow K$ is a nonexpansive mapping.

We will prove that for every $x \in K \cap S_R(z)$ and $\lambda > 1$ $\mathcal{J}_1^A x - z \neq \lambda(x - z)$. By contradiction, assume that there exist $x_0 \in K \cap S_R(z)$ and $\lambda_0 > 1$ such that $\mathcal{J}_1^A x_0 - z = \lambda_0(x_0 - z)$. Then, $\mathcal{J}_1^A x_0 = z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z) \in K$ and so

$$x_0 \in z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z) + f(z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z)) + N_K(z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z))$$

which implies that

$$(1 - \lambda_0)(x_0 - z) - f(z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z)) \in N_K(z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z)).$$

Then, bearing in mind the definition of N_K we have

$$\langle (1 - \lambda_0)(x_0 - z) - f(z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z)), J(y - z - \lambda_0(x_0 - z)) \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall y \in K$$

In particular, if $y = z \in K$

$$(1 - \lambda_0)\langle x_0 - z, J(-\lambda_0(x_0 - z)) \rangle + \lambda_0\langle f(z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z)), J(x_0 - z) \rangle \leq 0.$$

From (P_2) ,

$$(1 - \lambda_0)(-\lambda_0)R^2 + \lambda_0\langle f(z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z)), J(x_0 - z) \rangle \leq 0,$$

which implies

$$\langle f(z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z)), J(x_0 - z) \rangle \leq (1 - \lambda_0)R^2 < 0 \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, since $z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z) \in K$ and f is accretive

$$\langle f(x_0) - f(z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z)), J((1 - \lambda_0)(x_0 - z)) \rangle \geq 0$$

By using (4) we have

$$\langle f(x_0), J(x_0 - z) \rangle \leq \langle f(z + \lambda_0(x_0 - z)), J(x_0 - z) \rangle < 0$$

which contradicts the hypothesis of the theorem.

By Theorem 2.1 there exists a bounded approximate fixed point sequence to \mathcal{J}_1^A and by Theorem 9.1 in [14] this implies that there is a closed convex bounded set in K which is invariant under \mathcal{J}_1^A . Since X has the FPP we conclude that \mathcal{J}_1^A has a fixed point. \square

Corollary 3.1. *Let \mathbb{B} be a smooth space with the FPP and let $K \subset \mathbb{B}$ be a closed convex set. The variational inequality $VI(f, K)$ has a solution whenever $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is an accretive mapping satisfying the generalized coercivity condition at $x_0 \in K$ and $f + N_K$ has the range condition.*

Proof. Just apply Proposition 3.3 together with Theorem 3.1. \square

Corollary 3.2. *Let K be a closed convex subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} with the FPP. If $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is ψ -accretive at zero and $f + N_K$ has the range condition, then the problem $VI(f, K)$ has solution.*

Proof. It is a consequence of Proposition 3.2 and Theorem 3.1. \square

3.3. Examples

The following example shows that $f + N_K$ has the range condition is essential in the previous results.

Example 3.1. It is easy to check that the variational inequality $VI(f, K)$ does not have solution for $K = [-1, 1]$ and $f : [-1, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x + 2 & \text{if } -1 < x \leq 1, \\ -1 & \text{if } x = -1. \end{cases}$$

Notice that f is accretive. In fact, f is ϕ -strongly accretive with $\phi(t) = t$. Indeed, for $x, y \in (-1, 1]$, we have $\langle f(x) - f(y), J(x - y) \rangle = |x - y|^2 = \phi(|x - y|) |x - y|$. And for $x \in (-1, 1]$, we have $\langle f(x) - f(-1), J(x + 1) \rangle = (x + 3)(x + 1) \geq (x - (-1))^2$.

Furthermore, f is ψ -accretive at zero with $\psi(t) = t$, because $\langle f(x), J(x - (-1)) \rangle = f(x)(x + 1) \geq x + 1 = \psi(|x - (-1)|)$, for all $x \in (-1, 1]$.

We point out that the previous results fail because in this example $f + N_K$ does not have the range condition. Indeed, note that

$$x + f(x) + N_K(x) = \begin{cases} (-\infty, -2] & \text{if } x = -1, \\ \{2x + 2\} & \text{if } -1 < x < 1, \\ [4, +\infty) & \text{if } x = 1. \end{cases}$$

Then, there exists no point $x \in [-1, 1]$ such that $0 = x + f(x) + N_K(x)$.

It is easy to prove that if \mathbb{B} is a smooth Banach space and $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is an accretive mapping with the range condition, then $N_K + f$ has also the range condition. Next, we give two examples where $f + N_K$ enjoys the range condition and however f does not enjoy it.

Example 3.2. Consider $K = [a, \infty)$, with $a \in \mathbb{R}$. Let $f : [a, \infty) \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ be a continuous and nondecreasing function. Notice that f does not have the range condition because if we take $y \in [a, \infty)$ with $a \leq y < a + f(a)$ then there exists no $x \in [a, \infty)$ such that $y = x + f(x)$.

However, let us prove that $f + N_K$ has the range condition. By Remark 2.1 we know $N_K(x) = \{0\}$ for all $x > a$. Moreover,

$$N_K(a) = \{\xi \in \mathbb{R} : \xi(z - a) \leq 0 \forall z \in [a, \infty)\} = (-\infty, 0].$$

Thus, given $y \in [a, \infty)$, if $a \leq y < a + f(a)$ then $y \in a + f(a) + N_K(a)$ since $y - (a + f(a)) < 0$. And if $y \geq a + f(a)$ then there exists $x \in [a, \infty)$ such that $y = x + f(x) \in x + f(x) + N_K(x)$ since if we define $g : [a, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by $g(x) = x + f(x)$ it is clear that g is continuous and therefore $g([a, \infty)) = [a + f(a), \infty)$.

Example 3.3. Fix $1 < p < \infty$ and $a > 0$. Let \mathbb{B} be the smooth Banach space $L^p([0, 1], \mathbb{R})$ with its usual norm. Let $\beta : [a, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a nondecreasing, convex and continuous function with $\beta(a) > 0$. Consider the convex closed set $K := \{u \in \mathbb{B} : u \geq a, \beta(u) \in \mathbb{B}\}$. We define $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ as $f(u) = \beta(u)$. It is easy to see that f is accretive, see [3]. Moreover, f does not have the range condition. Indeed, it is enough to prove it for $\lambda = 1$: there exists $y \in K$ such that $y = x + f(x)$ is unsolvable in K . Just take $y \in \mathbb{B}$ such that $a \leq y(t) < a + \beta(a)$ for all $t \in [0, 1]$. In this case, if there was $x \in K$ such that $y = x + f(x)$ we would have that $y(t) = x(t) + \beta(x(t)) \geq a + \beta(a)$ for all $t \in [0, 1]$, which is a contradiction.

We now prove that $f + N_K$ has the range condition. Recall that the normalized duality mapping in $\mathbb{B} = L^p([0, 1], \mathbb{R})$ is given by $J(x) = |x|^{p-1} \text{sign}(x) \|x\|^{2-p}$, see [5] for more details. Let x_a be the constant function equals to a . Then, we have $L^p([0, 1], (-\infty, 0]) \subseteq N_K(x_a)$ since if $\xi(t) \leq 0$ a.e $t \in [0, 1]$ then

$$\int_0^1 \xi(t) |y(t) - a|^{p-1} \text{sign}(y(t) - a) dt \leq 0 \quad \text{for all } y \in K,$$

that is, $\xi \in N_K(x_a)$. Thus, given $y \in K$ we consider two cases:

- *Case 1.* If $a \leq y(t) \leq a + \beta(a)$ a.e. $t \in [0, 1]$, then $y \in x_a + f(x_a) + N_K(x_a) = a + \beta(a) + N_K(x_a)$ because the function $y - (a + \beta(a))$ belongs to $L^p([0, 1], (-\infty, 0])$ and therefore to $N_K(x_a)$.
- *Case 2.* The Lebesgue measure of the set $\Omega_1 := \{t \in [0, 1] : y(t) > a + \beta(a)\}$ is strictly positive. We take

$$w(t) := \begin{cases} (I + \beta)^{-1}(y(t)) & \text{if } t \in \Omega_1, \\ a & \text{if } t \in [0, 1] \setminus \Omega_1. \end{cases}$$

Note that, for each $t \in \Omega_1$, $w(t)$ is well-defined, because the monotonicity of β implies that the function $(I + \beta)^{-1} : [a + \beta(a), \infty) \rightarrow [a, \infty)$ is well-defined and, moreover, is nonexpansive.

It is clear that $w \in K$ and $\Theta := \{g \in \mathbb{B} : g \chi_{\Omega_1} = 0, g \chi_{[0, 1] \setminus \Omega_1} \leq 0\} \subseteq N_K(w)$, where χ_C denotes to the characteristic function of the subset C . Indeed, if $g \in \Theta$ then for all $z \in K$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{[0, 1]} g(t) |z(t) - w(t)|^{p-1} \text{sign}(z(t) - w(t)) dt \\ &= \int_{\Omega_1} g(t) |z(t) - w(t)|^{p-1} \text{sign}(z(t) - w(t)) dt \\ &+ \int_{[0, 1] \setminus \Omega_1} g(t) |z(t) - w(t)|^{p-1} \text{sign}(z(t) - w(t)) dt \\ &= \int_{[0, 1] \setminus \Omega_1} g(t) |z(t) - a|^{p-1} \text{sign}(z(t) - a) dt \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

which yields $g \in N_K(w)$. Therefore, we have $y \in w + f(w) + N_K(w)$ and we conclude that $f + N_K$ has the range condition.

3.4. *Without assuming that X has the FPP*

Theorem 3.2. *Let K be a closed convex subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . If $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is a ϕ -strongly accretive mapping such that $N_K + f$ has the range condition, then the following conditions are equivalent.*

- (a) *the variational inequality $VI(f, K)$ has a (unique) solution,*
- (b) *f satisfies condition $(C_{R,z}^+)$.*

Proof. We only prove (b) \Rightarrow (a). Since f is ϕ -strongly accretive, for $x, y \in K$ and $\xi_x \in N_K(x)$ and $\xi_y \in N_K(y)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \xi_x + f(x) - (\xi_y + f(y)), J(x - y) \rangle &= \langle \xi_x - \xi_y, J(x - y) \rangle + \langle f(x) - f(y), J(x - y) \rangle \\ &\geq \langle f(x) - f(y), J(x - y) \rangle \\ &\geq \phi(\|x - y\|) \|x - y\|, \end{aligned}$$

which implies $\|\xi + f(x) - (\eta + f(y))\| \geq \phi(\|x - y\|)$. Thus, if $A := N_K + f$ we get $|Ax - Ay| \geq \phi(\|x - y\|)$ for all $x, y \in K$.

By Proposition 2.1 we know that $\mathcal{A}_\lambda x \in A\mathcal{J}_\lambda^A x \forall x \in K$. If $\lambda = 1$, by taking $\mathcal{J}_1^A x$ and $\mathcal{J}_1^A y$ instead of x and y in the last inequality we get

$$\|x - \mathcal{J}_1^A x - (y - \mathcal{J}_1^A y)\| \geq \phi(\|\mathcal{J}_1^A x - \mathcal{J}_1^A y\|) \quad \text{for all } x, y \in \mathcal{R}(I + f). \quad (5)$$

As in the proof of Theorem 3.1 the conditions imposed on f allow us guarantee the existence of a bounded approximate fixed point sequence $\{x_n\}$ for \mathcal{J}_1^A . By using (5) we conclude that $\{\mathcal{J}_1^A(x_n)\}$ is a Cauchy sequence because $\{\mathcal{J}_1^A(x_n)\}$ is a bounded sequence (this fact is consequence of nonexpansiveness of \mathcal{J}_1^A) and for all bounded sequence $\{t_n\} \subset [0, \infty)$ we have $\phi(t_n) \rightarrow 0$ if and only if $t_n \rightarrow 0$ (this fact is consequence of the continuity of ϕ and $\phi(r) > 0$ for all $r > 0$). Hence, $\{\mathcal{J}_1^A(x_n)\}$ converges to a point $y \in K$. Since $\{x_n\}$ is an approximate fixed point sequence for \mathcal{J}_1^A it follows that $x_n \rightarrow y$ and so $\mathcal{J}_1^A y = y$. The uniqueness is a consequence of Proposition 3.6. \square

As a consequence of the above theorem and Proposition 3.4 we obtain the following result.

Corollary 3.3. *Let K be a closed convex subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} . Assume that $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is a ϕ -strongly accretive mapping such that $N_K + f$ has the range condition. If $\phi(r) \rightarrow \infty$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$, then the variational inequality $VI(f, K)$ has a unique solution.*

4. Projected dynamical systems and variational problem $VI(f, K)$

In 1994 Alber [1] introduced and studied several functionals in order to get different generalizations of the metric projection operator from Hilbert spaces to uniformly convex and uniformly smooth Banach spaces. Later, Kamimura and Takahashi [16] extended the definition of the generalized projection operator to reflexive, strictly convex and smooth Banach spaces.

Unless otherwise stated we assume that K to be a nonempty, closed and convex subset of a smooth, strictly convex and reflexive Banach space \mathbb{B} . Consider the Lyapunov functional $W : \mathbb{B} \times \mathbb{B} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given by $W(x, y) := \|x\|^2 - 2\langle x, J(y) \rangle + \|y\|^2$. We point out that if K is a closed convex subset of \mathbb{B} and $x \in K$, then the problem $\min_{y \in K} W(x, y)$ is uniquely solvable, see Proposition 3 in [16] for its proof. Then, the concept of metric projection can be extended to Banach spaces as follows.

Definition 4.1 ([16]). We define the generalized projection into K as the mapping $\Pi_K : \mathbb{B} \rightarrow K$ that associates to $x \in \mathbb{B}$ the minimum point of the functional $W(x, \cdot)$, that is, $\Pi_K(x)$ verifies that $W(x, \Pi_K(x)) = \inf_{y \in K} W(x, y)$.

The following result states a variational characterization for the generalized projection.

Lemma 4.1 ([16]). *Let K be a nonempty closed convex subset of a smooth, strictly convex and reflexive Banach space \mathbb{B} and let $(x, z) \in \mathbb{B} \times K$. Then, $z = \Pi_K x$ if and only if $\langle y - z, J(x) - J(z) \rangle \leq 0$ for all $y \in K$. In particular, $\Pi_K x = 0$ if and only if $\langle y, J(x) \rangle \leq 0$ for all $y \in K$.*

We now define a new mapping which will be used to get a relationship between the equilibrium points of a differential equation and the solutions of the variational problem $VI(f, K)$. In order to do this, for a nonempty subset K of \mathbb{B} , we denote $K' := \overline{\text{conv}}(J(K))$.

Remark 4.1. Note that if \mathbb{B} is a Hilbert space then $K' = K$.

Definition 4.2. Let K be a closed convex subset of a smooth strictly convex Banach space \mathbb{B} . We define the mapping $\Lambda^{K'} : \mathbb{B} \rightarrow J^{-1}(K')$ as $\Lambda^{K'} = J^{-1} \circ \Pi_{K'} \circ J$.

Notice that $\Pi_{K'}$ is the generalized projection taking as the framework the dual space \mathbb{B}^* . By using Lemma 4.1, we obtain a variational characterization of $\Lambda^{K'}$.

Lemma 4.2. *Let K be a nonempty closed convex subset of \mathbb{B} . Then, $\hat{x} = \Lambda^{K'}(x)$ if and only if $\langle x - \hat{x}, J(\hat{x}) - \varphi \rangle \geq 0$ for all $\varphi \in K'$.*

Proof. By using the variational characterization for Π_K we get:

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{x} = \Lambda^{K'}(x) &\iff J(\widehat{x}) = \Pi_{K'}(J(x)) \\ &\iff \langle J(\widehat{x}) - \varphi, J^{-1}(J(x)) - J^{-1}(J(\widehat{x})) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall \varphi \in K' \\ &\iff \langle x - \widehat{x}, J(\widehat{x}) - \varphi \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall \varphi \in K'.\end{aligned}$$

□

Recall that a nonempty subset K of \mathbb{B} is called a positive homogeneous subset if $\lambda K \subseteq K$ for all $\lambda > 0$.

Lemma 4.3. *Let K be a closed and positive homogeneous subset of \mathbb{B} . For each $x \in \mathbb{B}$ we have $\Lambda^{K'}(x) = \widehat{x}$ if and only if the following two properties are satisfied:*

$$(d_1) \langle x - \widehat{x}, J(\widehat{x}) \rangle = 0 \qquad (d_2) \langle x - \widehat{x}, \varphi \rangle \leq 0 \text{ for all } \varphi \in K'.$$

Proof. Assume that (d_1) and (d_2) hold. By subtracting, we get

$$\langle x - \widehat{x}, J(\widehat{x}) - \xi \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall \xi \in K' \tag{6}$$

By Lemma 4.2, this implies that $\widehat{x} = \Lambda^{K'}(x)$. Conversely, if $\widehat{x} = \Lambda^{K'}(x)$ then (6) holds. Since $0 \in K'$, from (6) we have $\langle x - \widehat{x}, J(\widehat{x}) \rangle \geq 0$. On the other hand, since K is a positive homogeneous set, it is easy to check that K' is also positive homogeneous. Hence, $J(\widehat{x}) \in K'$ implies $2J(\widehat{x}) \in K'$. Thus, again from (6), $\langle x - \widehat{x}, J(\widehat{x}) \rangle \leq 0$. Consequently $\langle x - \widehat{x}, J(\widehat{x}) \rangle = 0$ and we get (d_1) . This together with (6) give us the conclusion in (d_2) .

□

Recall that a nonempty subset C of \mathbb{B} is called a closed point convex cone if C is closed and $C + C \subseteq C$, $\lambda C \subseteq C$ for all $\lambda \geq 0$, and $C \cap (-C) = \{0\}$. On the other hand, the dual cone [1] of a closed point convex cone C is denoted by C^0 and is defined as $C^0 = \{\varphi \in \mathbb{B}^* : \langle x, \varphi \rangle \leq 0, \text{ for all } x \in C\}$.

Proposition 4.1. *Let $C \subset \mathbb{B}$ be a closed point convex cone, $C' = \overline{\text{conv}}\{J(C)\}$ and $C'^0 \subseteq \mathbb{B}$ its polar cone. Then, for every $x \in \mathbb{B}$, if $\widehat{x} = \Lambda^{C'}(x)$ there exists $y \in C'^0$ such that $x = \widehat{x} + y$ and $\langle y, J(\widehat{x}) \rangle = 0$.*

Proof. Note that C is positive homogeneous, because C is a closed point convex cone. By (d_2) in Lemma 4.3, $\widehat{x} = \Lambda^{C'}(x)$ implies that $\langle x - \widehat{x}, \varphi \rangle \leq 0$ for all $\varphi \in C'$. This means that $x - \widehat{x} \in C'^0$ and so $x - \widehat{x} = y$, with $y \in C'^0$. By (d_1) in Lemma 4.3 we have $\langle y, J(\widehat{x}) \rangle = 0$. □

Definition 4.3. Let K be a nonempty subset of a smooth Banach space \mathbb{B} and $x_0 \in \mathbb{B}$. We define the tangent cone to K at the point x_0 as

$$\mathcal{T}_K(x_0) := \overline{\bigcup_{\lambda > 0} \lambda(K - \{x_0\})}.$$

Remark 4.2. Note that if K is closed and convex, then for each $x_0 \in K$ the tangent cone $\mathcal{T}_K(x_0)$ as well as the normal cone $\mathcal{N}_K(x_0)$ are two closed point convex cones.

Definition 4.4. Let K be a closed convex bounded set in \mathbb{B} and $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$. Consider the differential equation:

$$\begin{cases} u'(t) = \Lambda^{\mathcal{T}'(u(t))}(-f(u(t))), & \text{for } t \in [0, \infty) \\ u(0) = x_0 \in K. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathcal{T}'(x) := \overline{\text{conv}}(J(\mathcal{T}_K(x)))$. We say that $x : [0, \infty) \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow K$ is a solution to the initial value problem (7) if x is an absolutely continuous function such that $x(0) = x_0$ and $x'(t) = \Lambda^{\mathcal{T}'(x(t))}(-f(x(t)))$ for almost everywhere $t \geq 0$.

Remark 4.3. Notice that in the setting of Hilbert spaces we have $W(x, y) = \|x - y\|^2$. Then, Π_K is the metric projection P_K . Furthermore, we know that $J = J^{-1}$ is the identity mapping. Thus, $\Lambda^{\mathcal{T}'(x)} = P_{\mathcal{T}_K(x)}$. Therefore,

$$u'(t) = \Lambda^{\mathcal{T}'(u(t))}(-f(u(t))) = P_{\mathcal{T}_K(u(t))}(-f(u(t))) = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} \frac{P_K(u(t) - \lambda f(u(t))) - u(t)}{\lambda}$$

that is, in Hilbert space the initial value problem (7) coincides with a projected dynamical system, see [11] and the references given there.

As a consequence of Proposition 4.1 we get a relationship between the solution to the differential equation given in (7) and a certain differential inclusion involving to the normal cone. To be more precise, we have the following result.

Proposition 4.2. *Let K be a closed and convex subset of \mathbb{B} with $0 \in K$ and $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$. Then, $x : I \rightarrow X$ is a solution for (7) if and only if x satisfies the differential inclusion*

$$\begin{cases} u'(t) + \mathcal{N}_K(u(t)) \ni -f(u(t)), & \text{for a.e. } t \in [0, \infty) \\ u(0) = x_0 \in K. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Proof. For sake simplicity, for each $t \geq 0$, we denote $x(t)$ by x_t . Suppose that $x : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is a solution for (7). Then x satisfies that $x'_t = \Lambda^{\mathcal{T}'(x_t)}(-f(x_t))$ for a.e. $t \geq 0$. By Proposition 4.1 we can write $\Lambda^{\mathcal{T}'(x_t)}(-f(x_t)) = -f(x_t) - y(x_t)$, with $y(x_t) \in \mathcal{T}'(x_t)^0$, that is, $\langle y(x_t), \varphi \rangle \leq 0$ for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{T}'(x_t)$. Thus, in particular $\langle y(x_t), \varphi \rangle \leq 0$ for all $\varphi \in J(\mathcal{T}_K(x_t))$ and therefore $y(x_t) \in \mathcal{N}_K(x_t)$.

Now let $x : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ be an absolutely continuous function satisfying the differential inclusion $x'_t \in -f(x_t) - \mathcal{N}_K(x_t)$ for a.e. $t \geq 0$. By definition of $\mathcal{N}_K(x_t)$, we have

$$\langle -f(x_t) - x'_t, J(y - x_t) \rangle \leq 0 \quad \text{a.e } t \geq 0, \forall y \in K. \quad (9)$$

Then,

$$\langle -f(x_t) - x'_t, \varphi \rangle \leq 0 \quad \text{a.e } t \geq 0, \quad \forall \varphi \in \mathcal{T}'(x_t) \quad (10)$$

In particular, for $\varphi = J(x_t) \in \mathcal{T}'(x_t)$, we get $\langle -f(x_t) - x'_t, J(x_t) \rangle \leq 0$ a.e. $t \geq 0$. But, from (9) for $y = 0 \in K$, we have $\langle -f(x_t) - x'_t, J(x_t) \rangle \geq 0$ a.e. $t \geq 0$. Thus,

$$\langle -x'_t - f(x_t), J(x_t) \rangle = 0 \quad \text{a.e } t \geq 0. \quad (11)$$

Considering (10) and (11), from Lemma 4.3 it follows that $\Lambda^{\mathcal{T}'(x_t)}(-f(x_t)) = x'_t$ for almost everywhere $t \geq 0$. \square

Recall that $x \in K$ is called a critical point for differential equation (7) if $u'(t) = 0$ a.e $t \in I$.

We now show that there is a fundamental relation between the critical points of the differential equation (7) and the solutions of the variational inequality $VI(f, K)$.

Proposition 4.3. *Let K be a closed and convex subset of \mathbb{B} and $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$. Then, the solutions to the variational inequality $VI(f, K)$ coincide with the critical points of the ordinary differential equation (7).*

Proof. Note that x^* is a critical point of (7) if, and only if, $\Lambda^{\mathcal{T}'(x^*)}(-f(x^*)) = 0$. Lemma 4.2 yields $\langle -f(x^*), \varphi \rangle \leq 0$ for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{T}'(x^*)$. In particular, we deduce $\langle f(x^*), J(x - x^*) \rangle \geq 0$ for all $x \in K$, that is, x^* is a solution of variational inequality $VI(f, K)$.

We now assume that x^* is a solution of $VI(f, K)$, that is, $\langle f(x^*), J(x - x^*) \rangle \geq 0$ for all $x \in K$. By using the homogeneity of J , we infer that

$$\langle -f(x^*), J(\lambda(x - x^*)) \rangle = -\lambda \langle f(x^*), J(x - x^*) \rangle \leq 0$$

for all $\lambda > 0$ and $x \in K$. This implies that $\langle -f(x^*), \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i J(\lambda(x_i - x^*)) \rangle \leq 0$ for all $\lambda > 0$, $x_i \in K$ and $\alpha_i \geq 0$ with $\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i = 1$. Then, $\langle -f(x^*), \varphi \rangle \leq 0$ for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{T}'(x^*)$. By Lemma 4.2, we obtain $\Lambda^{\mathcal{T}'(x^*)}(-f(x^*)) = 0$, which means that x^* is a critical point of (7). \square

Theorem 4.1. *Let K be a closed and convex subset of \mathbb{B} . Suppose that $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is accretive and $f + \mathcal{N}_K$ has the range condition. Then, the initial valued problem (8) has a unique strong solution for each $x_0 \in K$. Furthermore, if $0 \in K$ then this solution is also the solution of the differential equation (7).*

Proof. Note that the initial valued problem (7) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{cases} u'(t) + A(u(t)) \ni 0, & \text{for a.e. } t \geq 0 \\ u(0) = x_0 \in K, \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $A := f + \mathcal{N}_K$ is an accretive operator with the range condition. In this case, from Corollary 1.1 in [3], we infer that (12), and therefore (8), has a unique strong solution for each $x_0 \in K$ and such solution can be given by Crandall-Liggett's formula

$$u(t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(I + \frac{t}{n} A \right)^{-n} (x_0).$$

Moreover, if $0 \in K$, by Proposition 4.2 this unique strong solution of (8) is also solution of (7). \square

Theorem 4.2. *Let K be a closed and convex subset of \mathbb{B} . If $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is ψ -accretive at zero and $f + \mathcal{N}_K$ has the range condition, then each strong solution of Problem (8) converges strongly as $t \in \infty$ to the solution of $VI(f, K)$.*

Proof. Since f is ψ -accretive at zero and \mathcal{N}_K is accretive we infer that $A := f + \mathcal{N}_K$ is ψ -accretive at zero. Indeed, if we fix $z_0 \in K$, for any $x \in K$ and $y \in A(x)$ we have that there exists $\xi \in \mathcal{N}_K(x)$ such that $y = f(x) + \xi$ which implies

$$\begin{aligned} \langle y, J(x - z_0) \rangle &= \langle f(x) + \xi, J(x - z_0) \rangle \\ &= \langle f(x), J(x - z_0) \rangle + \langle \xi, J(x - z_0) \rangle \\ &\geq \psi(x - z_0), \end{aligned}$$

that means that $A = f + \mathcal{N}_K$ is ψ -accretive at zero. From Theorem 4.1, we know that, given a point $x \in K$, there exists a unique strong solution $u_x : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ of Problem (8). Thus we can apply [9, Theorem 8] in order to obtain the strong convergence. \square

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